

Principals' Perception of Personnel Management Functions as Determinants of Quality Assurance in Secondary Schools in Enugu State

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Abstract

The study examined principals' perception of personnel management functions as determinants of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised all 295 principals (194 male and 101 female principals) of public secondary schools in Enugu State. There was no sampling because the population was manageable. Instrument for data collection was a researcher structured questionnaire titled "Personnel Management Functions Questionnaire (PMFQ)". Validation of the instrument was done by three experts. Two of them were from the Department of Educational Management, while the other one was from Measurement and Evaluation unit of the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education. All the experts were from the Faculty of Education, ESUT, Agbani. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha statistic which yielded 0.79 and 0.81 for clusters 1 and 2 respectively. The overall reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.80, indicating a high reliability of the instrument for the study. The research questions were answered using mean scores and cluster mean, while the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at .05 level of significance. Results of data analysis indicated that principals perceived staff development function and performance appraisal as determinants of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State to a great extent. In view of the findings, the study recommended that principals should from time to time organize workshops/seminars for their teachers for capacity building. Also, annual performance appraisal for teachers is equally vital.

Keywords: Principals, Personnel Management Functions, Quality Assurance

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Introduction

Education at the secondary school level which is the focus of this study is the level of education after primary school. Secondary education has witnessed tremendous expansion in the past five decades. The situation has been attributed to a number of factors among which are National Policy on Education in which education is to be adopted as the foundation

of national development (Ugochukwu, 2020). Aroge (2012) posited that everyone who is concerned about the academic performance of students in secondary schools will agree that the improvement of teaching quality is a high priority in any of the educational programmes. The head of secondary schools is known as principal.

A principal is a person with the highest authority or most important position in an organisation most especially of school system. According to Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), the secondary school principal is the administrative head of secondary school, charged with the responsibility of running the day-to-day activities of the school and is responsible for all that goes on in the school. Shama & Sandana in Uwakwe (2017), stated that they take decisions daily that affect the lives of students and the personnel they manage.

The effective management of secondary school lies in the hands of the principals. Sen (2012) defined management as the process which involves the coordination of the activities of others in order to achieve results not achievable by an individual acting alone, rather a process by which scarce resources are combined to achieve given ends. Okon (2011) defined educational management as all those processes involved in the efficient and effective conduct of the affairs, obligations and activities of a school. Nwankwo (2012) defined educational management as a process that involves planning, organizing, communicating and coordinating all school's activities with the aim of realizing the school objectives. The principal as the administrative head of a secondary school and needs other staff both teaching and non-teaching to keep the activities of the school moving well. Hence, the principal must be knowledgeable enough and must have wide experience to manage other personnel in his establishment.

Personnel management is defined as obtaining, using, and maintaining satisfied employees (Ahammad, 2017). Kuntu (2013) defined personnel management as that part of management function which is concerned with people at work and their relationship within an organization or enterprise. Personnel management is an administrative function of a business that exists to provide the

personnel needed for organizational activities and to manage the general employee-employer relationship. These are common to all managers including personnel managers. The planning function of a personnel manager pertains to the steps taken in determining a course of action. Samuelson (2013) listed personnel management practices or functions as recruitments, selection, training and development, job evaluation with salaries/wages, formulation of manpower policies, provision of data for planning and decision making; co-ordination of performance appraisals, personnel research, health and safety administration, as well as administration of discipline. However, the researcher focused on the following personnel management functions: staff professional and development performance appraisal.

Professional development is the process of continuously updating teachers' knowledge, skills and interests in the chosen field (Nakpodia in Olohundare & Shola, 2020). Staff professional development is one of the important strategies for addressing the challenge of teacher quality (Muraya & Wairimu, 2020). Staff professional development involves critically examining teaching, attending workshops, professional meetings and reflection sessions, sharing with other teachers, reading publications and, thereby, gaining valuable experiences in the profession (Muraya & Wairimu, 2020). The benefits of professional development to teachers is to assist teachers obtain higher teaching qualifications; acquire more conceptual and technical knowledge, skills and competencies in their teaching subjects (Osokoya, 2012). Thus, Hervie & Winful (2018) noted that training works as a catalyst which provokes a significant change in a teacher, redefines roles, broadens vision and enhances the attributes of a teacher. Through professional development programmes such as seminars, conferences, workshops, lectures,

symposia and further studies for acquisition of higher teaching qualifications; teachers' knowledge, skills and techniques are expected to be updated to make them assist the schools to achieve effectiveness (Olohundare & Shola, 2020).

Performance appraisal is the process of evaluating how well employers perform their jobs as compared to a set of standards and then communicating that information to those employees. Performance appraisal is the system of evaluating employee's performance relative to his or her job requirements (Muhammad, Arif & Asghar, 2019). Chapman (2011) posited that performance appraisals are essential for the effective management and evaluation of staff. Performance appraisal is an effective tool in forming job standards and judging employee's actual performance relative to those standards. It is a systematic process that improves the effectiveness of the organization (Muhammad, Arif & Asghar, 2019). This study ascertained the extent to which performance appraisal is a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State. The appraisal system creates an optimistic impact on the teaching quality and performance of teachers (Saunders, 2010). Performance appraisal may be a key in the quality assurance exercise in education system.

Quality assurance is part of quality management focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled (Denchukwu, 2020). Quality assurance is a way of preventing mistakes or defects in a system. No doubt, quality assurance in secondary schools hinges to a great extent on principals' ingenuity in managing school personnel effectively (Harrison, 2011). Quality assurance process is an act of managing and utilization of human and material resources towards the realization of stated educational objectives (Ayeni, 2012). According to Ifedili (2015), quality

assurance is the process of ensuring that the educational outputs (students) are processed with all required staff and quality programmes, facilities and materials to meet the universal standard.

At this point, it is important to consider an independent variable that may be an important determinant of quality assurance. Such a variable is gender. Gender has been defined and described variously by scholars. Gender, according to Onyeonuru (2015), is referred to as the differentiation in roles between men and women which is different from sex but construed by society through socialization. According to Okeke in Nnamani & Oyibe (2016) gender is referred to as socially constructed roles and socially learned behaviours and expectations associated with males and females.

The concern about the quality of secondary education is on the increase in Nigeria. This comes at a time of growing awareness of mass failure of senior secondary school students in public examination conducted by West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO). Hence, there are growing complaints by parents, heads of tertiary institutions and employers of graduates of this level of education as regards the secondary school graduates poor performance, and as a result cannot understand the challenges ahead (Fasasi & Oyeniran, 2014). Hence, the need for principals' perception of personnel management functions as determinants of quality assurance in secondary schools.

Perception refers to the set of processes one uses to make sense of the different stimuli one is presented with. According to Romanov (2011), perception is one's ability to understand the difference. It is also the way in which something is regarded, understood or interpreted. One's perceptions are based on how one interprets different sensations. The perceptual process begins

with receiving stimuli from the environment and ends with our interpretation of those stimuli. Perception involves the five senses; touch, sight, taste, smell and hearing.

There has been steady decline in teachers' instructional task performance and students' academic performance which depicts non-realization of quality assurance in secondary schools (Ayeni, 2012). However, a cursory look at public secondary school system in Nigeria, particularly in Enugu State in recent times suggests that the schools are not living up to expectation in the provision of quality education in the three domains of learning, namely: cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains, thereby, making schools ineffective in producing the needed quality human resource for national development. It is against the above thrust that this study determined principals' perception of personnel management functions as determinants of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Today, in Enugu State, Nigeria, the poor performance of secondary school students in both internal and external examinations has become a major concern of stakeholders, educators, parents, employers, employees and indeed the society at large. There has been a public outcry on the continual decline in the quality of education in the country especially as indicated in public examination and the performance of education outputs that are inadequate for employment. This is because the results derived from the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE), especially the West African Senior School Certificate Examinations (WASSCE) and National Examination Council (NECO) over the years have not been commensurate with the purpose in which they were made. The results in external examinations remain the major indicator of quality in the secondary educational system. The abysmal performance has

squarely been blamed on the teachers who are accused of apathy and high levels of inefficiency in the discharge of duties. Unfortunately, the deplorable working conditions under which teachers break their backs to prepare the future leaders of the country have not been seriously considered by the authorities. Poor infrastructure, insufficient logistics, slackness in the upholding of ethical conducts, low salaries and inadequate reward system are characterised with the teaching profession. Furthermore, teaching under unsuitable and deplorable conditions lead to negative effect on students. It is, therefore, not surprising that students continue to have bad results at their final examinations and their inability to write, speak and comprehend in simple English Language. It is against this background that the researcher is motivated to investigate personnel management functions as determinants of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State. This is in relation to staff professional development and performance appraisal. The problem of this study is, therefore, put in a question form thus: "To what extent do principals perceive personnel management functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State?"

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the extent to which principals perceive personnel management functions are determinants of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the extent to which principals perceive staff development function is a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State;
2. ascertain the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal function is a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do principals perceive staff professional development function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State?
2. To what extent do principals perceive performance appraisal function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive staff professional development function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

HO₂: Significant difference does not exist between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Nworgu (2015) defined descriptive survey research design as a design that aims at collecting data and describing them in a systematic way. The population for the study comprised all 295 principals (194 male and 101 female principals) of public secondary schools in Enugu State. There was no sampling because the population was manageable. Instrument for data collection was a researcher structured questionnaire titled "Personnel Management Functions Questionnaire (PMFQ)". The instrument

contained a total of 20 items structured on a four point rating scale of Very Great Extent (VGE) – 4 points, Great Extent (GE) – 3 points, Low Extent (LE) – 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) – 1 point. To those options, numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 were assigned respectively for the items. Validation of the instrument was done by three experts. Two of them were from the Department of Educational Management, while the other one was from Measurement and Evaluation unit of the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education.

All the experts were from the Faculty of Education, ESUT, Agbani. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha statistic which yielded 0.79 and 0.81 for clusters 1 and 2 respectively. The overall reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.80, indicating a high reliability of the instrument for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In rating the mean, each response option had a numerical value based on real limit of numbers: VGE = 3.50-4.00; GE= 2.50-3.49; LE = 1.50-2.49; VLE = 0.00-1.49. The interpretation of the test of hypotheses was based on the significance (sig.) values from the SPSS output. The null hypotheses were not rejected when the probability values were greater than 0.05, but were rejected when the probability values were less than 0.05.

Data Analysis and Results Presentation

Research Question 1: To what extent do principals perceive staff professional development function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive staff professional development function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools

ITEMS		Principals =274			Teachers n=768		
S/N	Staff professional development determine quality assurance when they are involved in:	\bar{x}	SD	Dec	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
1	workshop.	2.94	.82	GE	3.02	.80	GE
2	educational conferences.	2.95	.80	GE	2.96	.82	GE
3	information and Communication Training programme.	3.01	.81	GE	3.02	.83	GE
4	in-service training programmes.	2.93	.81	GE	3.00	.81	GE
5	refresher course programmes for newly recruited teacher.	2.99	.82	GE	2.98	.80	GE
6	seminars.	3.01	.84	GE	2.94	.82	GE
7	further studies.	3.00	.83	GE	3.02	.81	GE
8	professional training by resource persons.	3.04	.80	GE	2.98	.83	GE
9	special function for training in areas like sports to keep them fit.	2.91	.82	GE	3.00	.82	GE
10	vocation courses.	3.01	.83	GE	3.02	.83	GE
Cluster Mean/SD		2.98	.82	GE	2.99	.82	GE

The data analysis on Table 1 shows that the male principals' mean ranged from 2.91 to 3.04, while the female principals' mean ranged from 2.94 to 3.02. The values of the cluster mean are 2.98 and 2.99 for male and female principals. They also have standard deviations of .82 and .82. The closeness of the standard deviations showed that the respondents

were homogenous in their responses. The outcome of the above Table revealed that principals perceive staff professional development to a great extent functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Question 2: To what extent do principals perceive performance appraisal function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State?

Table 2: Mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools

ITEMS		Male Principals N=194			Female Principals N=101		
S/N	Performance appraisal determines quality assurance when teachers:	\bar{x}	SD	Dec	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
11	prepare their lessons adequately.	3.05	.82	GE	2.94	.82	GE
12	are regular to their classes.	3.03	.86	GE	2.96	.81	GE
13	cover their scheme before exams.	2.91	.78	GE	2.96	.84	GE
14	give assignments regularly.	2.94	.82	GE	3.03	.80	GE
15	mark students' assignments regularly.	2.97	.82	GE	3.06	.82	GE
16	are assigned to their areas of specialization.	3.05	.82	GE	3.02	.82	GE
17	are punctual to their classes.	2.92	.80	GE	3.00	.81	GE
18	write good lesson notes.	3.02	.80	GE	2.92	.83	GE
19	use appropriate instructional materials during teaching and learning process.	2.99	.79	GE	2.99	.81	GE
20	adhere to the rules and regulations of the school.	2.92	.83	GE	2.98	.81	GE
Cluster Mean/SD		2.98	.81	GE	2.99	.82	GE

The data analysis on Table 2 above shows that the male principals' mean ranged from 2.91 to 3.05, while the female principals' mean ranged from 2.92 to 3.06. The values of the cluster mean are 2.98 and 2.99 for male and female principals. They also have standard deviations of .81 and .82. The standard deviation shows unanimity in the responses of the respondents. This signifies that principals perceive performance appraisal to a great extent functions as a determinant

of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive staff professional development function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive staff professional development function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male Principals	194	2.98	.82	293	.361	H ₀₁ not rejected
Female Principals	101	2.99	.82			

Data in Table 3 for male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive staff professional development functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State show that at 1040 degree of freedom, the p-value was .361. The outcome of the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance set for this study. This signifies that the null hypothesis was not rejected and, therefore, there was no significant difference between the mean

ratings of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive staff professional development functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

HO₂: Significant difference does not exist between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal function as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male Principals	194	2.98	.81	293	.705	H ₀₂ not rejected
Female Principals	101	2.99	.82			

Data in Table 4 for male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State show that at 1040 degree of freedom, the p-value was .705. The outcome of the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance set for this study. This implies that the null hypothesis was not rejected and, therefore, there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study showed that principals perceive staff professional development functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State to a great extent. The finding of the study is in accordance with Hervie & Winful (2018), who noted that training works as a catalyst which provokes a significant change in a teacher, redefines

roles, broadens vision and enhances the attributes of a teacher. The finding is also in agreement with Olohundare & Shola (2020) who posited that through professional development programmes such as seminars, conferences, workshops, lectures, sypmosia and further studies for acquisition of higher teaching qualifications; teachers’ knowledge, skills and techniques are expected to be updated to make them assist the schools to achieve effectiveness. Further finding indicated that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals perceive staff performance development functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State. The outcome of the hypothesis is in agreement with Hervie & Winful (2018) who posited that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of the respondents on staff professional development as a determinant of quality assurance of principals in secondary schools.

The finding of the study showed that principals perceive performance appraisal functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State to a great extent. The finding is in agreement to Endale (2015) who posited that performance appraisal is a critical determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools. The finding is also in accordance with Saunders (2010) who posited that the appraisal system creates an optimistic impact on the teaching quality and performance of teachers. Further findings revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals perceive performance appraisal functions as a determinant of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the study concludes that principals perceive personnel management functions in terms of staff professional development and performance appraisal as determinants of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State to a great extent. Good quality staff professional development and performance appraisal in secondary schools make important contributions to developing the professional skills of teachers and ensuring the best quality learning experiences for students.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Principals should from time to time organize workshops/seminars for their teachers for capacity building.
2. Annual performance appraisal for teachers is equally vital in order to actualize quality assurance in secondary schools.

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